

Oxidation of Allyl Alcohol by Diperiodatonickelate(IV) in Aqueous Alkaline Medium

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The rate of oxidation of allyl alcohol (AA) by alkaline diperiodatonickelate(IV) (DPN) is found to decrease with increase in periodate concentration and increase with increasing OH⁻ concentration. The reaction is first order in [DPN] and fractional order in [AA] and [OH⁻]. Based on the results a suitable mechanism is proposed. The rate law derived from this mechanism is verified and some reaction constants are also found.

Studies of oxidation using nickel(IV) complex as oxidants in the form of nickel(IV) oxime and nickel(IV) periodate are scanty¹. Reduction of nickel(IV) complexes has received considerable attention in order to understand the nature of intermediate oxidation states of nickel such as nickel(III). Indeed, stable nickel(III) complexes are known². Studies involving nickel(IV) periodate (DPN) as oxidant are limited since its solubility and stability in aqueous medium are small. Nevertheless, nickel(IV) periodate oxidation of some organic compounds like aliphatic amines, alcohols and acids has been studied in aqueous alkaline medium³. In such studies, the reactive species of nickel(IV) periodate is involved with the substrate in a single-step reaction. In view of the multiple equilibria embracing the different nickel(IV) periodate species and the complexity of the title reaction, a detailed study of the reaction was undertaken.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry was 1 : 1 (equation 1) as found in case of reaction solutions containing different sets of concentrations of DPN and AA at fixed OH⁻ concentration of 0.20 mol dm⁻³ after approximately 4 h of reaction.

Pseudo-first order runs with excess [AA] led to log [DPN] vs time plots which were linear beyond 80%. Furthermore, variation of [DPN] in such runs did not lead to any significant change in the k_{obs} . From the data of pseudo-first order constant (k_{obs}) at different [AA] and constant [DPN], a plot of log k_{obs} vs log [AA] led to the order in [AA] of ~0.5. The order in [OH⁻], other conditions being constant, was ~0.50. Prior addition of reaction products and salts like sodium sulphate, nitrate and chloride do not affect the reaction. Added periodate decreased the rate, the order in [IO₄⁻] being ~0.5. Ionic strength did not

significantly alter the rate. Dielectric constant, however, changed the rate as added t-butyl alcohol lowers the k_{obs} value. Variation of temperature between 25 and 45° led to $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ values of 43.5 (±2.0) kJ mol⁻¹ and -143 (±6) JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively.

The rate law for the title reaction follows,

$$\text{Rate} = k \frac{[\text{DPN}][\text{AA}]^{0.5} [\text{OH}^-]^{0.5}}{[\text{IO}_4^-]^{0.5}} \quad (2)$$

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [DPN], [AA], [OH⁻] AND [IO₄⁻] ON DPN-AA REACTION*

Temp.=25°, I=0.70 mol dm ⁻³				
[DPN] × 10 ⁵	[AA] × 10 ³	[OH ⁻]	[IO ₄ ⁻] × 10 ⁴	k_{obs} × 10 ³ s ⁻¹
1.0	5.0	0.20	—	2.30
2.0	5.0	0.20	—	2.30
3.0	5.0	0.20	—	2.25
5.0	5.0	0.20	—	2.30
7.0	5.0	0.20	—	2.25
10	5.0	0.20	—	2.30
5.0	0.50	0.20	—	0.76
5.0	1.0	0.20	—	0.90
5.0	2.0	0.20	—	1.45
5.0	3.0	0.20	—	1.75
5.0	4.0	0.20	—	2.10
5.0	5.0	0.20	—	2.35
5.0	7.0	0.20	—	2.70
5.0	10	0.20	—	3.10
5.0	5.0	0.10	—	1.62
5.0	5.0	0.20	—	2.24
5.0	5.0	0.30	—	3.10
5.0	5.0	0.40	—	3.40
5.0	5.0	0.50	—	3.45
5.0	5.0	0.70	—	4.10
5.0	5.0	0.20	1.0	2.10
5.0	5.0	0.20	2.0	1.60
5.0	5.0	0.20	4.0	1.12
5.0	5.0	0.20	6.0	0.96
5.0	5.0	0.20	8.0	0.84
5.0	5.0	0.20	10.0	0.70

*All concentration are in mol dm⁻³.

The water soluble nickel(IV) periodate complex is reported to be [Ni(HIO₆)₂(OH)₂]⁶⁻. However,

in an aqueous alkaline medium and in high pH range employed in this study, periodate is unlikely to exist as HIO_6^{4-} (as present in the complex) as is evident from its involvement in the multiple equilibria (3) to (5) depending on the pH of the solution,

Periodic acid (H_6IO_6) exists in acid medium⁵ and also as H_4IO_6^- around a pH of 7. Thus, under the alkaline conditions, the main species is expected to be $\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}$ and $\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6^{3-}$. At higher concentrations, periodate also tends to dimerise. Hence, it may be expected that the soluble complex is likely to be $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6)_2(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$, a conclusion also supported by earlier reports³.

The results of rate increase with alkalinity and the rate decrease with increasing periodate concentration, suggest that equilibria of different nickel(IV) periodate complexes matter. It may be expected that a lower periodate complex such as a monoperiodatonickelate(IV) (MPN) is more important in the reaction than the diperiodatonickelate(IV) (DPN).

The fractional order in $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ might also be due to this reason.

Therefore, MPN might be the main reactive form of the oxidant. Since the unsaturated organic compounds are known⁶ to be resistant to oxidation by one-electron oxidants, a free radical pathway for the reaction is to be discounted. Such a conclusion is also reinforced by the absence of polymerisation on addition of monomers like acrylonitrile and acrylamide to the reaction solution. The fractional order in the substrate, allyl alcohol (AA), presumably results from a complex formation between the oxidant and substrate prior to the formation of the products. Indeed, it is to be noted that the Michaelis-Menten plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{AA}]$ shows an intercept in agreement with such a complex formation. These results indicate a mechanism of the type presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1 leads to rate law (6), K_4 , K_5 and K_6 being the constants of the different equilibria and

Scheme 1

k is the rate constant of the decomposition of the complex C.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= -\frac{d[\text{Ni}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}}{dt} \\ &= \frac{kK_4K_5K_6[\text{Ni}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{OH}^-][\text{AA}]}{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_4[\text{OH}^-][\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_4K_5[\text{OH}^-] + K_4K_5K_6[\text{AA}][\text{OH}^-]} \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

or,

$$\begin{aligned} k_{\text{obs}} &= \frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{Ni}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}}} \\ &= \frac{kK_4K_5K_6[\text{OH}^-][\text{AA}]}{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_4[\text{OH}^-][\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + K_4K_5[\text{OH}^-] + K_4K_5K_6[\text{AA}][\text{OH}^-]} \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

The form (7) may be transformed into a form (8) suitable for verification,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} &= \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{kK_4K_5K_6[\text{OH}^-][\text{AA}]} \\ &\quad + \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{kK_5K_6[\text{AA}]} + \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]}{kK_6[\text{AA}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

Other conditions being constant, plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ against each of $1/[\text{OH}^-]$, $1/[\text{AA}]$ and $1/[\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{2-}]$ should be linear as is actually found (Fig. 1). From the slope and intercept, the values of K_4 , K_5 , K_6 and k could be derived as $17.8 (\pm 2) \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $2.4 \times 10^{-4} (\pm 3 \times 10^{-5}) \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $266 (\pm 20) \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $4.0 \times 10^{-3} (\pm 5.0 \times 10^{-5}) \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively.

Fig. 1. Verification of rate law (6) in the form of (8) (conditions are same as in Table 1).

The negligibly small effect of ionic strength on the reaction is presumably due to the fact that the reaction is between a neutral and a charged species (Scheme 1). Since the product is more polar than the reactant, the activated complex is expected to be highly polar and as a result, the complex tends to bind the solvent molecules much more strongly than is the case with the reactant molecules. This effect is expected to result in a considerably negative entropy of activation as is found and also the negative slope of the $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/D$ plot.

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals and double-distilled water were used. Allyl alcohol (Koch-light) solutions were standardised⁷ with chloramine-T and the excess estimated iodometrically. Solutions of nickel(IV) periodate complex⁸ were prepared in aqueous alkaline media at 50°. Nickel was estimated gravimetrically as the dimethylglyoxime complex. The product acrolien was found by spot test⁹. KOH and KNO₃ were used to provide the required alkalinity and ionic strength respectively in the reaction solutions.

Kinetics were followed by mixing the previously thermostatted reactant solutions of DPN and AA which also contained the required amounts of KOH and KNO₃. The absorbance of DPN was measured on a Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer at 410 nm. Other constituents of the reaction solution did not absorb significantly at this wavelength. DPN concentrations between 1.0×10^{-5} and 2.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ in 0.20 mol dm⁻³ alkali obey Beer's law with $\epsilon = 3900 (\pm 5\%) \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Runs were followed under pseudo-first order conditions with AA in excess over that of DPN at $25 \pm 0.2^\circ$ unless otherwise stated. Duplicate runs agreed within $\pm 5\%$.

References

1. D. H. MACARTNEY and A. MCAULEY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, 22, 2062; S. ACHARYA, G. NEOGI, R. K. PANDA and D. RAMASWAMY, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1982, 14, 1253.
2. R. I. HAINES and A. MCAULEY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1981, 39, 77; K. NAG and A. CHAKRAVARTHY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, 33, 87.
3. U. CHANDRAIAH, J. A. KHAN, C. P. MURTHY and S. KANDLIKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, 26, 481; J. A. KHAN, U. CHANDRAIAH, B. K. KUMAR and S. KANDLIKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, 29, 241.
4. C. E. CROUTHAMEL, H. V. MEEK, D. S. MARTIN and C. V. BANKS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3031.
5. C. E. CROUTHAMEL, H. V. MEEK and D. V. MARTIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 82.
6. J. S. LITTLER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 382.
7. D. S. MAHADEVARPA and H. M. K. NAIDU, *Talanta*, 1973, 20, 349.
8. P. RAY, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1957, 5, 201.
9. I. L. UZDINA, *Hig. Truda*, 1937, 15, 63.